

The matching equivalent classes of $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)$

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10450099>

Published Date: 01-January-2024

Abstract: Completely characterize the matching equivalent classes of $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)$, by the property of graph's matching polynomial and its maximum roots.

Keywords: Matching polynomial, Matching equivalence, Matching uniqueness, The maximum real roots.

I. INTRODUCTION

All graphs considered in this paper are undirected and simple (i.e., loops and multiple edges are not allowed). Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E(G) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m\}$, where $|V(G)| = n$ is the order and $|E(G)| = m$ is the size of G . A spanning subgraph H is called a matching of G , if every connected component of H is isolated edge or isolated vertex. k -matching of G is a matching with k edges. In [1] E. J. Farrell denote the matching polynomial as

$$\mu(G, x) = \sum_{k \geq 0} (-1)^k p(G, k) x^{n-2k},$$

where $p(G, k)$ is the number of k -matchings of G .

Two graphs G and H are called matching-equivalent if $\mu(G, x) = \mu(H, x)$, and denoted by $G \sim H$. The disjoint union of two graphs G and H , denoted by $G \cup H$, is the graph with vertex set $V(G) \cup V(H)$ and edge set $E(G) \cup E(H)$. kG denotes the disjoint union of k copies of G . Let $M(G)$ be the largest matching root of $\mu(G, x)$. We denote by P_n ($n \geq 1$), C_n ($n \geq 3$) a path and a cycle of order n , respectively. A graph $D_{m,n}$ ($m \geq 3, n \geq 1$) is defined as the graph obtained by identifying one end of the path P_{n+1} with a vertex of the cycle C_m . By $T(a, b, c)$ denote the tree which has one 3-degree vertex u and three 1-degree vertices v_1, v_2, v_3 and the distance between u and v_1, v_2, v_3 are a, b, c , respectively. Let P_{n-2} be a path with vertices sequence $1, 2, \dots, n-2$, I_n ($n \geq 6$) denotes the tree obtained by adding pendant edges at vertices 2 and $n-3$ of P_{n-2} , respectively. For a graph G , let G^c be the complement of G . The classes of matching equivalent graphs determined by G under $\sim$ is denoted by $[G]$. For undefined terminology and notations we refer to references [2]. In this paper, we Completely characterize the matching equivalent classes of $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)$.

II. BASIC LEMMA

Lemma 2.1 ([1]): Let G be a graph with k components $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_k$. Then $\mu(G, x) = \prod_{i=1}^k \mu(G_i, x)$.

Lemma 2.2 ([1]): Let $e = uv \in E(G)$. Then $\mu(G, x) = \mu(G - e, x) - \mu(G - \{u, v\}, x)$.

Lemma 2.3 ([1]): Let G be a connected graph and $u \in V(G)$, $e \in E(G)$. Then $M(G)$ is a single root of $\mu(G, x)$ and $M(G) > M(G - u)$, $M(G) > M(G - e)$.

Lemma 2.4 ([3]): Let G be a connected graph. Then

(1) $M(G) < 2$ if and only if $G \in \Omega_1 = \{K_1, P_n, C_n, T(1,1,n), T(1,2,i) (2 \leq i \leq 4), D_{3,1}\}$;

(2) $M(G) = 2$ if and only if $G \in \Omega_2 = \{K_{1,4}, T(2,2,2), T(1,3,3), T(1,2,5), I_n, D_{3,2}, D_{4,1}\}$.

Lemma 2.5 ([4]): Let $M(G) < 2$. Then graph G is matching uniquely if and only if

$$G = kK_1 \cup m_2P_2 \cup m_3P_3 \cup [\cup_{i \geq 2} m_{2i}P_{2i}] \cup [\cup_{j \geq 3} n_jC_j] \cup dD_{3,1} \cup eT(1,2,3) \cup fT(1,2,4),$$

where $kn_j = m_i n_{i+1} = m_2d = m_3d = n_3e = n_3n_5f = n_5n_9f = 0$ and k, m_i, n_j, d, e, f are non-negative integer.

Lemma 2.6 ([5]): (1) $P_{2m+1} \sim P_m \cup C_{m+1}$ ($m \geq 2$) (2) $T(1,1,n) \sim K_1 \cup C_{n+2}$ (3) $T(1,2,2) \sim P_2 \cup D_{3,1}$

(4) $K_1 \cup C_6 \sim P_3 \cup D_{3,1}$ (5) $K_1 \cup C_9 \sim C_3 \cup T(1,2,3)$ (6) $K_1 \cup C_{15} \sim C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4)$

Lemma 2.7 ([6]): (1) $D_{3,2} \sim D_{4,1}$ (2) $K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \sim I_6$ (3) $T(2,2,2) \sim P_2 \cup D_{3,2}$ (4) $T(1,3,3) \sim P_3 \cup D_{3,2}$

(5) $T(1,2,5) \sim P_4 \cup D_{3,2}$ (6) $K_1 \cup I_6 \sim P_2 \cup K_{1,4}$ (7) $P_{m-4} \cup I_n \sim P_{n-4} \cup I_m$ ($m, n \geq 6$)

(8) $I_{2m-3} \sim I_m \cup C_{m-3}$ ($m \geq 6$)

Lemma 2.8 ([5]): $G \sim H$ if and only if $G^c \sim H^c$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 3.1 Let $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)]$ be The classes of matching equivalent graphs of $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)$. Then

(1) If $n \neq 1, 3, 4, 7, 13$, $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)] = \{P_4 \cup P_2 \cup K_{1,4} \cup C_{n+2}, K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup T(1,1,n), 2K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup C_{n+2}, P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2}, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,n), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2}, P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,n), P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_{n+2}, P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,n), P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_{n+2}\}$;

(2) If $n = 1$, $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,1)] = \{P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_2 \cup C_3, P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_5, P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_3, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,1), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_3, I_8 \cup K_1 \cup P_5, P_4 \cup I_9 \cup K_1\}$;

(3) If $n = 3$, $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,3)] = \{P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_2 \cup C_5, P_2 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_9, P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_5, I_6 \cup K_1 \cup P_9, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,3), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_5, P_2 \cup I_{13} \cup K_1, P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,3), P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_5, 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup P_9, P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,3), P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_5, 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup P_9\}$;

(4) If $n = 4$, $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,4)] = \{T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup T(1,1,4), T(1,2,5) \cup 2K_1 \cup C_6, T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,1}, P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_6, P_4 \cup P_3 \cup I_6 \cup D_{3,1}, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,4), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_6, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,1}, P_3 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,2,2), P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,4), P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_6, P_4 \cup P_3 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup D_{3,1}, P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,4), P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_6, P_4 \cup P_3 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup D_{3,1}\}$;

(5) If $n = 7$, $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,7)] = \{T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup T(1,1,7), T(1,2,5) \cup 2K_1 \cup C_9, T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3), P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_9, P_4 \cup I_6 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,7), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_9, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3), P_5 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,2,3), K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,7), 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_9, K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3), K_1 \cup P_4\}$

$UD_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,7), 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_9, K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3) \}$;

(6) If $n = 13$, $[P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,13)] = \{K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup T(1,1,13), 2K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup C_{15}, K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4), P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15}, P_4 \cup I_6 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4), C_3 \cup P_9 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,2,4), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,13), P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15}, P_2 \cup I_8 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4), P_5 \cup I_8 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4), P_2 \cup I_{13} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,4), P_5 \cup I_{13} \cup T(1,2,4), K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,13), 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_{15}, K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4), K_1 \cup C_3 \cup P_9 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,2,4), K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,13), 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_{15}, K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4), K_1 \cup C_3 \cup P_9 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,2,4) \}$.

Proof: Let $H \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n)$, then $M(H) = M(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n))$, By Lemma 2.4, we obtain $M(H) = M(I_6) = 2$. There must be a connected component H_1 in H belonging to the set Ω_2 . Let $H = H_1 \cup H_2$. Thus, we distinguish with the following cases according to $M(I_6)$.

Case 1: If $H_1 = K_{1,4}$, then $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim K_{1,4} \cup H_2$. By $K_{1,4} \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim P_3 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2} \sim P_2 \cup P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup C_{n+2}$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup P_4 \cup C_{n+2}$.

Subcase 1.1: If $n \neq 1, 3$, then $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup P_4 \cup C_{n+2}$;

Subcase 1.2: If $n=1$, by Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup P_4 \cup C_3 \sim P_4 \cup P_5$;

Subcase 1.3: If $n=2$, by Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup P_4 \cup C_5 \sim P_2 \cup P_9$.

Case 2: If $H_1 = T(2,2,2)$, then $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim T(2,2,2) \cup H_2$. By $K_1 \cup P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim K_1 \cup T(2,2,2) \cup H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_2 \cup D_{3,2} \cup H_2 \sim P_2 \cup I_6 \cup H_2$, we have $P_2 \cup H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_{n+2}$. By Lemma 2.5 and Lemma 2.6, this case does not exist.

Case 3: If $H_1 = T(1,3,3)$, then $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim T(1,3,3) \cup H_2$. By $K_1 \cup P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim K_1 \cup T(1,3,3) \cup H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,2} \cup H_2 \sim P_3 \cup I_6 \cup H_2$, we have $P_3 \cup H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_{n+2}$. By Lemma 2.5 and Lemma 2.6, this case does not exist.

Case 4: If $H_1 = T(1,2,5)$, then $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim T(1,2,5) \cup H_2$. By $K_1 \cup P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup H_2$.

Subcase 4.1: If $n \neq 4, 7, 13$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim 2K_1 \cup C_{n+2}$;

Subcase 4.2: If $n = 4$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup T(1,1,4) \sim 2K_1 \cup C_6 \sim K_1 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,1}$;

Subcase 4.3: If $n = 7$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup T(1,1,7) \sim 2K_1 \cup C_9 \sim K_1 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3)$;

Subcase 4.4: If $n = 13$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup T(1,1,13) \sim 2K_1 \cup C_{15} \sim K_1 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4)$.

Case 5: If $H_1 = I_m$, then $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim I_m \cup H_2$.

Subcase 5.1: If $n \neq 1, 3, 4, 7, 13$, By Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7, we have $I_m \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2} \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2}$. So, if $m = 6$, we have $H_2 \sim P_4 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim P_4 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2}$; if $m = 8$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim P_2 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2}$.

Subcase 5.2: If $n=1$, By Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7, we have $I_m \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,1) \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_3 \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,1) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_3 \sim K_1 \cup P_5 \cup I_8 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup I_9$.

So, if $m=6$, we have $H_2 \sim P_4 \cup T(1,1,1) \sim P_4 \cup K_1 \cup C_3$; if $m=8$, $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup T(1,1,1) \sim P_2 \cup K_1 \cup C_3 \sim K_1 \cup P_5$; if $m=9$, $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4$.

Subcase 5.3: If $n=3$, By Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7, we have $I_m \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,3) \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_5 \sim K_1 \cup P_9 \cup I_6 \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,3) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_5 \sim K_1 \cup P_2 \cup I_{13}$. So, if $m=6$, we have $H_2 \sim P_4 \cup T(1,1,3) \sim P_4 \cup K_1 \cup C_5 \sim K_1 \cup P_9$; if $m=8$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup T(1,1,3) \sim P_2 \cup K_1 \cup C_5$; if $m=13$, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_2$.

Subcase 5.4: If $n=4$, By Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7, we have $I_m \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,4) \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_6 \sim P_3 \cup P_4 \cup I_6 \cup D_{3,1} \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,4) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_6 \sim P_2 \cup P_3 \cup I_8 \cup D_{3,1} \sim I_8 \cup P_3 \cup T(1,2,2)$. So, if $m=6$, we have $H_2 \sim P_4 \cup T(1,1,4) \sim P_4 \cup K_1 \cup C_6 \sim P_3 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,1}$; if $m=8$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup T(1,1,4) \sim P_2 \cup K_1 \cup C_6 \sim P_2 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,1} \sim P_3 \cup T(1,2,2)$.

Subcase 5.5: If $n=7$, By Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7, we have $I_m \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,7) \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_9 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,7) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_9 \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup C_3 \cup P_2 \cup I_8 \cup \sim P_5 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,2,3)$. So, if $m=6$, we have $H_2 \sim P_4 \cup T(1,1,7) \sim P_4 \cup K_1 \cup C_9 \sim P_4 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3)$; if $m=8$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup T(1,1,7) \sim P_2 \cup K_1 \cup C_9 \sim P_2 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3) \sim P_5 \cup (1,2,3)$.

Subcase 5.6: If $n=13$, By Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7, we have $I_m \cup H_2 \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,13) \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15} \sim P_4 \cup I_6 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim C_3 \cup P_9 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,13) \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15} \sim P_2 \cup I_8 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim P_2 \cup I_{13} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim P_5 \cup I_{13} \cup T(1,2,4)$. So, if $m=6$, we have $H_2 \sim P_4 \cup T(1,1,13) \sim P_4 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15} \sim P_4 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim C_3 \cup P_9 \cup T(1,2,4)$; if $m=8$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup T(1,1,13) \sim P_2 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15} \sim P_2 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim P_5 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,4)$; if $m=13$, we have $H_2 \sim P_2 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim P_5 \cup T(1,2,4)$.

Case 6: If $H_1 = D_{3,2}$, then $P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim D_{3,2} \cup H_2$. By Lemma 2.7, we have $K_1 \cup P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup H_2 \sim I_6 \cup H_2$.

Subcase 6.1: If $n \neq 3,4,7,13$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,n) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_{n+2}$;

Subcase 6.2: If $n=3$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,3) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_5 \sim 2K_1 \cup P_9$;

Subcase 6.3: If $n=4$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,4) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_6 \sim K_1 \cup P_3 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,1}$;

Subcase 6.4: If $n=7$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,7) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_9 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3)$;

Subcase 6.5: If $n=13$, By Lemma 2.6, we have $H_2 \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup T(1,1,13) \sim 2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_{15} \sim K_1 \cup P_4 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4) \sim K_1 \cup C_3 \cup P_9 \cup T(1,2,4)$.

Case 7: If $H_1 = D_{4,1}$. By $D_{3,2} \sim D_{4,1}$, it is similar to Case 6. The proof is omitted.

The proof of Theorem 3.1 is complete.

By Theorem 3.1 and Lemma 2.8, we have Theorem 3.2:

Theorem 3.2 Let $[(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n))^c]$ be The classes of matching equivalent graphs of $(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n))^c$. Then

(1) If $n \neq 1,3,4,7,13$, $[(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,n))^c] = \{(P_4 \cup P_2 \cup K_{1,4} \cup C_{n+2})^c, (K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup T(1,1,n))^c, (2K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup C_{n+2})^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2})^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,n))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_{n+2})^c, (P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,n))^c, (P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup$

$$C_{n+2})^c, (P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,n))^c, (P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_{n+2})^c \};$$

$$(2) \text{ If } n=1, [(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,1))^c] = \{(P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_2 \cup C_3)^c, (P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_5)^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_3)^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1, 1,1))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_3)^c, (I_8 \cup K_1 \cup P_5)^c, (P_4 \cup I_9 \cup K_1)^c \};$$

$$(3) \text{ If } n=3, [(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,3))^c] = \{(P_4 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_2 \cup C_3)^c, (P_2 \cup K_{1,4} \cup P_9)^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_5)^c, (I_6 \cup K_1 \cup P_9)^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,3))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_5)^c, (P_2 \cup I_{13} \cup K_1)^c, (P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,3))^c, (P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_5)^c, (2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup P_9)^c, (P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,3))^c, (P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_5)^c, (2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup P_9)^c \};$$

$$(4) \text{ If } n=4, [(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,4))^c] = \{(T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup T(1,1,4))^c, (T(1,2,5) \cup 2K_1 \cup C_6)^c, (T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,1})^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_6)^c, (P_4 \cup P_3 \cup I_6 \cup D_{3,1})^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,4))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_6)^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup P_3 \cup D_{3,1})^c, (P_3 \cup I_8 \cup T(1, 2,2))^c, (P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,4))^c, (P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_6)^c, (P_4 \cup P_3 \cup K_1 \cup D_{3,2} \cup D_{3,1})^c, (P_4 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,4))^c, (P_4 \cup 2K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_6)^c, (P_4 \cup P_3 \cup K_1 \cup D_{4,1} \cup D_{3,1})^c \};$$

$$(5) \text{ If } n=7, [(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,7))^c] = \{(T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup T(1,1,7))^c, (T(1,2,5) \cup 2K_1 \cup C_9)^c, (T(1,2,5) \cup K_1 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3))^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_9)^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,7))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_9)^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3))^c, (P_5 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,2,3))^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,7))^c, (2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_9)^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3))^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,7))^c, (2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_9)^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,3))^c \};$$

$$(6) \text{ If } n=13, [(P_4 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,1,13))^c] = \{(K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup T(1,1,13))^c, (2K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup C_{15})^c, (K_1 \cup T(1,2,5) \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15})^c, (P_4 \cup I_6 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (C_3 \cup P_9 \cup I_6 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup T(1,1,13))^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup K_1 \cup C_{15})^c, (P_2 \cup I_8 \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (P_5 \cup I_8 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (P_2 \cup I_{13} \cup C_3 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (P_5 \cup I_{13} \cup T(1, 2, 4))^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,1,13))^c, (2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_{15})^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{3,2} \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (K_1 \cup C_3 \cup P_9 \cup D_{3,2} \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,1,13))^c, (2K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_{15})^c, (K_1 \cup P_4 \cup D_{4,1} \cup C_3 \cup C_5 \cup T(1,2,4))^c, (K_1 \cup C_3 \cup P_9 \cup D_{4,1} \cup T(1,2,4))^c \}.$$

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